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Organizational Structure and Different Areas of Social Responsibility of Managers

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Abstract

In this paper, the relationship between organizational structure and different areas of social responsibility of managers has been studied in private and state departments and organizations in Rafsanjan. Statistical population includes all managers of private and state departments, institutes and organizations in Rafsanjan and since volume of statistical population was small, statistical sample was considered equally with statistical population. Census was used in this research. Two questionnaires were used as tools for data gathering. A researcher made questionnaire has been used for different areas of social responsibility of managers that includes 30 questions and Sashkin & Morris's questionnaire for evaluating organizational structure that includes 20 questions with some modifications. They both were applied after determination of validity and reliability. In this research, different kinds of inferential statistics were used to analyze data including Candle's correlation test and Spearman's correlation coefficient. All statistical analyses were done by SPSS software. Significance difference of the test has been considered $\alpha = 0.05$.

Results of research showed that:

- 1- There is a relation between organizational structure and different areas of social responsibility of managers
- 2- Organic organizational structure faces higher social responsibility of managers than mechanic structure
- 3- There is a relationship between organizational structure and components of different areas of social responsibility of managers (consideration of basic norms of the organization, meeting personnel's needs, commitment to serve clients, environmental responsibility of managers and consideration of cultural values).

Keywords: structure, organizational structure, social responsibility, different areas of social responsibility

Introduction

Social responsibility of organization is a term that recently has been introduced in management world. Regarding different cases in management, this word has been dedicated different titles. For some people it is a joint responsibility and for others it is the first step taken voluntarily and still for others, it is a social joint responsibility. Whatever it is called, it is important that its principles remain uniformly and equally. So it is a positive voluntary innovation and it seems to be beyond accepting legal duties in different environmental, economical and social domains. A question always is brought to minds that what obstacles are there on the way of social responsibility of managers and their organizations? One of these obstacles can be type of organizational structure. From human researches' point of view done on organizations, there are many theorists and social philosophers who thought that organizations are the only suitable way to access peace, development and social justice (H.Hall, Persian translation, 43:2004). If organizations do not respect their social objectives, they will be surrounded by pollution, poverty, diseases, discrimination and disturbance and if they do not look at this by providence, these problems will finally seize them by collar. It is while that traditional managers should be intellectual and provident leaders so that in far horizons they should not ignore movements and turbulence of waves in endless sea and since in today philosophy of management, being responsible for people and society is an important part of every organization, it can be said that if managers were being evaluated based on their achievements in profitability but now they will be evaluated with an index more comprehensive than profitability. In order that managers become successful in this evaluation, they should forget to consider details and go beyond boundaries of their organization and consider social issues. They should able to integrate, evaluate and analyze internal and external organizational issues. It needs some changes in traditional objectives, structure and practices of organizations (Alvani, 322:2000).

Problem statement

Organizational structure is an organizational framework that refers to a degree of formality, centralization and complexity (Moghimi, 41:2001). Formality is to the extent that rules, policies and procedures are present and are used for organizational operations. Centralization refers to how powers are distributed in the organization and complexity includes four types: environment, the more environmental complexity, the more complex the organizations, horizontal separation refers to number of minor units, skills and activities of an organization. Vertical separation is the number of hierarchical levels and geographical and spatial scatters of organization (Moghimi, 42:2001).

Two experts, Boronz and Stalker, presented a general pattern for organizational structure in 1961

1- Mechanical structure that is known by features such as complexity and high formality and centralization. These structures are suitable for repeated tasks and activities.

2- Organic or biologic structures which are relatively flexible and adaptable. They highlight horizontal relations instead of vertical one. It insists on information exchange instead of issuing orders (Robinz, Persian translation, 181:2004).

In general, every organization moves in direction of one of these two structures. If organization fluctuates between constant and variable events, the structure will be in fluctuation between these two forms so in most of organizations, mechanical and organic structures both are available in managerial system (Shafartiz, Persian translation, 397:2000). Today, in addition to their traditional tasks that are realization of organizational goals, organizations are responsible for other activities that are called social responsibility of organizations. It includes meeting needs of society and citizens (Alvani& Ghasemi, 1:1998). Social responsibility is managers' obligation of business organizations and private sector and they should decide in a way that improves public well being in addition to making profit (Haghighi, 4:1994). In fact, social responsibility is that society expects organizations

to act in direction of public advantage, maintaining environment and settling social problems in addition to their main goals (Najafbeigi, 326:2000). Paying attention to social issues needs to make necessary structures in organizations and allocation of financial and human sources to them (Alvani, 315:2000). It is evident that none of organizations can be existed lonely and they are not a goal in themselves rather each of them is one member of a society and they have been brought for the sake of the society. Therefore, instead of insisting on maximum profit, social factors should be considered including clients' satisfaction, suppliers, shareholders, staff, unions, government and society in general (Gholipoor, 280:2001). On the other word, society has some expectations and wants from organizations and these wants can determine ranges of managers' social responsibility. Ranges of managers' social responsibility include staff, customer, environment, cultural values and organizational norms (Alvani&Ghasemi, 50:1998). In reality, organizational social responsibility refers to its relation to society, participation and making social goals as one of its elements (Gholipoor, 278:2001). After determining their goals, organizations determine their functions proportional to social goals and values then they design suitable structures in order to realize those functions (Gholipoor, 1280:2001). In recent years, one of social problems is lack of consideration and commitment of organization to their social responsibility that attracted many experts in different societies. A conscious society is active to solve social problems and asks managers specially top ones that what steps do they take to play their social responsibility and why they don't take a further step? On the other hand, what obstacles are there on the way of their social responsibility?

The present study done among managers of private and state organizations and offices in Rafsanjan is tried to find a suitable answer to the question whether or not there is a relation between organizational structure and ranges of social responsibility of managers.

Research objective

The goal is to identify and describe the relationship between organizational structure and beds of managers' social responsibilities in private and state organizations and offices in Rafsanjan.

Research place and subject matter ranges

In this research, relation between organizational structure in two dimensions, organic and mechanical, (as predictor variables) and beds for social responsibility from Alvani's point of view including basic norms of organization, staff, client, environment and cultural values (as benchmark variables) was dealt with in private and state organizations and offices in Rafsanjan.

Operational definition of words

1- Organizational structure:

In the present study, organizational structure has been revised using Sashkin& Morris's questionnaire and will be evaluated after determination of its validity and reliability. It has 20 questions and the score given to the respondents determines the kind of organizational structure ranged from very mechanical to very organic.

2- Beds for social responsibilities

In present study, areas of social responsibility include 5 components (basic norms of organization, staff, client, environment, cultural values) that will be measured by researcher-made questionnaire after determination of its validity. The score given to the respondents will determine areas of managers' social responsibility.

Theoretical framework of the research

Barons and Stalker studied 20 English and Scottish companies in 1961 and found that organizational structure and its management is different regarding different environmental conditions. They found that organizational structure can form dynamically from mechanical condition with minimum changes to completely variable and flexible (Najafbeigi, 69:2000). Work division and hierarchical supervision are emphasized in mechanical systems while in organic systems, responsibility and membership in multiple groups will be developed. Mechanical systems encourage centralized decision while division of responsibility and control in throughout the organization are encouraged in organic system (French, Bell, Persian translation, 47:2000). In mechanical system, organizational activities are divided into elements and specialized tasks and goals of each organizational unit will be defined exactly by top managers of the organization. A clear example is bureaucratic system of classic school and hierarchy of orders (Najafbeigi, 87:2000). Bureaucracy can be changed into an iron cage for humans and destroys human values (Gholipoor, 268:2001) and it is no doubt that systems should respect cultural values and natural needs of humans and commit to such relationship (Tehrani, 42:1995). Therefore, organizational structure without paying attention to human and his interest and desires cannot lead organization to its goal and helps several obstacles while reaching goals. Responsibility of employers can be compromised due to lack of having necessary autonomy for controlling affairs (Hicks, 1997). The fact is that organizations relying on their profits and due to responsibilities for goals determined for them try to achieve more and more goal realization. The attempt in direction of organizational goals cause management to ignore its environment and limits its tasks to inside the organization (Alvani, Ghasemi, 1: 1998). Organizational structure is a way by which organizational activities are divided, controlled and organized. In general, if the structure is high in complexity, formality and centralization of decision system, job satisfaction is reduced, employees will feel alien while in organic structures, satisfaction and cohesion are increased (Ghasemi, 588:2003). Therefore, some structures encourage responsibility, creativity and innovation and others prevent from such behaviors. Using a correct structure causes improvements in performance (French, Bell, Persian translation, 19:2000). Today, separation of organizations from social environment and managers' engagement in organizational goals and their indifference to social problems cause a new era in management that is called managers' social responsibility. In fact, social responsibility of organization implies on its relation with society, participation and supplying social goals as one of its elements (Gholipoor, 278:2001). When an organization is considered as a social system, the first step is to determine specific values and goals for which social system is organized (Persons, 56:2004). Social value system should be considered for determination of organizational goal because social values and goals should be met by the organization and it is the only way that the organization can survive. After determining its goal proportional to social goals and values, the organization can specify its functions then design suitable structures to realize those functions (Gholipoor, 128:2001). It is evident that social responsibility is social expectation from organizations and should be act in direction of public advantages, protection of environment and solving social problems along with its basic goals (Najafbeigi, 226:2000). Paying attention to social responsibility requires necessary structures in organization and allocation of financial and human sources (Alvani, 315:2000). On the other hand, governmental organizations are faced bureaucratic structures more than elsewhere. These structures prevent government from serving customers by problematic regulations and laws. Finally, all these issues cause state organizations to be unable to do their social responsibilities (Gholipoor, 285:2001). So the researcher after studying different books and papers about organizational structure and social responsibility decided to present his study based on organizational structure, division presented by Barons and Stalker, social responsibility of managers represented by Alvani

Analytical model of research

Concept → element → index

Research hypotheses

Major hypotheses

- 1- There is a relationship between organizational structure and areas of social responsibility of managers in private and state organizations and offices in Rafsanjan.
- 2- Organic organizational structure is followed by higher social responsibility of managers than mechanical structure.

Minor hypotheses

- 1- There is a relationship between organizational structure and consideration of basic norms of the organization.
- 2- There is a relation between organizational structure and meeting needs of staff.
- 3- There is a relation between organizational structure and commitment to serve customers.
- 4- There is a relation between organizational structure and environmental responsibility of managers.
- 5- There is a relation between organizational structure and consideration of cultural values.

Research methodology

This is a descriptive correlative research and it is the relation between two or more variables or two or more set of data. This relationship can be measured by correlation coefficient (Bast, Persian translation, 1995). It is objectively a kind of practical research and data gathering was done by a field study.

Statistical population

Statistical population is a set of people or units that has at least one common characteristic. In every research, statistical population is one which the researcher tends to study about variable characteristics of its units (Moghimi, 2001:63). Statistical population of this research is all managers of departments, institutes, state centers in Rafsanjan. The number of State and private organizations and departments in Rafsanjan is 73. In mentioned organizations, the manager is one who is in position of management and the number of them is 73.

Sampling method and sample volume

Since investigation about all member of the society is time consuming and it is not cost effective, the researcher had to take sampling (Moghimi, 36:2006). In present study, considering statistical population volume (organizational managers) is small, statistical sample was considered equally with statistical population and a kind of census was used in this study. Totally, 73 questionnaires were distributed among managers of which 71 questionnaires were returned. Based on sample volume $n=71$, estimation error was calculated as follows:

$$n_{\max} = \frac{z^2}{4e^2} = \frac{3.8416}{4e^2} = 71 \quad e = 0.12$$

Tools of data gathering

In order to gather data for areas of social responsibility of managers, researcher made questionnaire was used. It includes 30 questions (each component, 6 questions) and was designed in a closed form based on Likert scale. In order to measure organizational structure, Morris and Sashkin's questionnaire was used with some modifications. It has 20 questions and was designed in a close form based on Likert scale.

This questionnaire studied organizational structure ranged from very mechanical to very organic.

Validity and reliability

Validity: in present study, in order to determine validity of questionnaires (structure and ranges of social responsibility of managers), content method was used by 5 university professors so validity of the structural questionnaire was 91% and that of areas of social responsibility of managers was 92%.

Reliability: in order to measure reliability of measurement tool (questionnaires), Kranbach’s alpha was used so reliability related to areas of social responsibility of managers was 93.79% and that of organizational structure was 87.64%.

Data analysis

In present study, different tables and graphs were used to describe gathered data. Candle and Spearman’s correlation test have been used to determine correlation between main variables. All statistical analyses were done by SPSS software.

Results

Correlation test

Hypothesis 1: there is a relation between organizational structure and areas of social responsibility of managers

H₀: there is no relationship between organizational structure and ranges of social responsibility of managers.

H₁: there is a relation between organizational structure and ranges of social responsibility of managers.

Considering that Candle and Spearman’s correlation coefficients between above two variables are 0.348 and 0.406 respectively and their significances are 0.001 and 0.000, so null hypothesis will be rejected. Increase in organizational structure (from mechanical towards organic) increases areas of social responsibility of managers.

Table 1: calculation of correlation and significance of the first main hypothesis

Organizational Structure	areas of social responsibility					
	Candle correlation			Spearman correlation		
	Correlation coefficient	significance	frequency	Correlation coefficient	significance	frequency
	0.348	0.001	71	0.406	0.000	71

Main hypothesis 2: organic organizational structure is followed by more social responsibility of managers than mechanical structure.

H₀: distribution of ranges of social responsibility of managers is the same in different levels of organizational structure

H₁: distribution of ranges of social responsibility of managers is not the same in different levels of organizational structure.

Considering that X^2 statistics and test significance were obtained 17.865 and 0.000 respectively so null hypothesis is rejected meaning that distribution of areas of social responsibility of managers is not the same in different levels of organizational structure so it can be concluded that increase in organizational structure (from mechanical towards organic) increases ranges of social responsibility of managers.

Minor hypothesis 1: there is a relationship between organizational structure and consideration of basic norms of the organization.

H_0 : there is no relationship between organizational structure and consideration of basic norms of the organization.

H_1 : there is a relationship between organizational structure and consideration of basic norms of the organization.

Considering that Candle and Spearman’s correlation coefficients between above two variables are 0.350 and 0.487 respectively and their significance is 0.000, null hypothesis is rejected.

Table 2: calculation of correlation and significance of the first minor hypothesis

Organizational Structure	Consideration of basic norms					
	Candle correlation			Spearman correlation		
	Correlation coefficient	significance	frequency	Correlation coefficient	Significance	Frequency
	0.350	0.000	71	0.487	0.000	71

The minor hypothesis 2: there is a relation between organizational structure and meeting needs of staff.

H_0 : there is no relation between organizational structure and meeting needs of staff.

H_1 : there is a relation between organizational structure and meeting needs of staff.

Considering that Candle and Spearman’s correlation coefficients between above two variables are 0.390 and 0.538 respectively and their significance is 0.000, so null hypothesis is rejected.

Table 3: calculation of correlation and significance of the second minor hypothesis

Organizational Structure	Meeting staff’s needs					
	Candle correlation			Spearman correlation		
	Correlation coefficient	significance	frequency	Correlation coefficient	significance	Frequency
	0.390	0.000	71	0.538	0.000	71

The minor hypothesis 3: there is a relation between organizational structure and commitment to serve customers.

H_0 : there is no relation between organizational structure and commitment to serve customers.

H_1 : there is a relation between organizational structure and commitment to serve customers.

Considering that Candle and Spearman’s correlation coefficients between above two variables are 0.352 and 0.520 respectively and their significance is 0.000, so null hypothesis is rejected.

Table 4: calculation of correlation and significance of the third minor hypothesis

Organizational Structure	Commitment to serve customer					
	Candle correlation			Spearman correlation		
	Correlation coefficient	significance	frequency	Correlation coefficient	significance	Frequency
	0.352	0.000	71	0.520	0.000	71

The minor hypothesis 4: there is a relation between organizational structure and environmental responsibility of managers.

H₀: there is no relation between organizational structure and environmental responsibility of managers.

H₁: there is a relation between organizational structure and environmental responsibility of managers.

Considering that Candle and Spearman’s correlation coefficients between above two variables are 0.340 and 0.333 respectively and their significances are 0.002 and 0.001, so null hypothesis

is rejected.

Table 5: calculation of correlation and significance of the forth minor hypothesis

Organizational Structure	Environmental responsibility of managers					
	Candle correlation			Spearman correlation		
	Correlation coefficient	significance	frequency	Correlation coefficient	significance	Frequency
	0.340	0.002	71	0.333	0.001	71

The minor hypothesis 5: there is a relation between organizational structure and consideration of cultural values.

H₀: there is no relation between organizational structure and consideration of cultural values.

H₁: there is a relation between organizational structure and consideration of cultural values.

Considering that Candle and Spearman’s correlation coefficients between above two variables are 0.187 and 0.266 respectively and their significances are 0.027 and 0.025, so null hypothesis is rejected.

Table 6: calculation of correlation and significance of the fifth minor hypothesis

Organizational	Consideration of cultural values					
	Candle correlation			Spearman correlation		
	Correlation	significance	frequency	Correlation	significance	Frequency

Structure	coefficient			coefficient		
	0.187	0.027	71	0.266	0.025	71

Discussion

Theoretical evidences suggest that there is a relationship between ranges of social responsibility of managers and organizational structure. Obtained analyses showed that this relationship is present in the studied population. After insisting on the relationship between organizational structure and social responsibility, French (Persian translation, 19:1992) believed that some structures encourage responsibility, innovation and creativity and some others prevent these behaviors. A correct structure causes major improvement in performance. Alvani (315:2000) believed that paying attention to social issues requires making necessary structures in organization and allocation of human and financial sources for it. Regarding results obtained from research, middle of social responsibility of managers who are working in organizations with very mechanical organizational structure is low and middle of those who work in organizations with very organic organizational structure or combination of them is average. It can be said that in addition to relationship with ranges of social responsibility of managers, organizational structure plays a main role in reduction and increase of social responsibility of managers and regarding their specific features, organic structures that are very flexible and adaptable pave the way for social responsibility of managers. On the contrary, mechanical structure is considered as an obstacle in the way of social responsibility of managers. Obtained middles and box and scatter diagrams suggest that the more the movement of organizational structure from very mechanical to mechanic\organic one, the more the ranges of social responsibility of managers Gholipoor (128:2001) mentioned similar results and believed that mechanical structures need more discipline, rules and methodology and regulations designed as tool change into goal and objective. So what is existent prevents from what it should be. In this regard, the organization feels no responsibility due to the society and its goals are not accepted by public. It can be concluded that one of the main obstacles in the way of social responsibility of managers is presence of mechanical structures (bureaucratic). It is assumed that there is a relationship between organizational structure and consideration of basic norms in the organization and it was confirmed by obtained evidences meaning increase in organizational structure increases consideration of basic norms of organization by the managers. It seems that regarding specific features of mechanical structures such as concentration on decision, lack of taking feedback, lack of paying attention to staff ideas and prevention from innovation and creativity, obedience of employers, most of organizational norms have been destroyed such as organizational accountability, mutual support of employers and top managers, playing a positive role in the organization, commitment in the organization. The main goal in these structures is to reach organizational goals and its protection. Managers also use any instrument and method to reach these goals and explain their practice that by ignoring social regulation and values, they want to follow organizational profit so it compromises the popularity of organization and dedicates most of organizational norms to organizational profits. It is expected that there is a relationship between organizational structure and meeting employers' needs. Data analysis confirmed it. In addition, it was observed that meeting employers' needs in mechanic structure is lower than organic structures. It can be said in addition to the relation between meeting employers' needs and organizational structure; it plays an important role in increase or decrease of meeting employers' needs by the managers. The more the movement of organizational structure towards lack of flexibility, adaptability, concentration on decision and standardization, the less the ability of managers is in meeting employers' needs and their satisfaction. It is evident that organizational structure without paying attention to human, his interest and desires does not leads the organization to its goal rather makes several obstacles in the way of its goal. Analyses showed that there is a relationship between

organizational structure and commitment to serve customers so the more the movement of organizational structure towards features of organic structure, the more the commitment of managers to serve customers. On the contrary, the more the movement of organizational structure towards mechanical one (lack of deviation of standards and instructions, obeying rules and regulations, hierarchy of official authorities, being disagreeable with modification of methods and procedures), the less the commitment of managers is to serve customers. Extreme reliance on regulations which have been changed into goals causes customer to fear and suspect powerful official institutions. Gholipoor (285:2001) has mentioned similar results and stated that governmental organizations face with bureaucratic structures more than elsewhere. These structures prevent government from serving customers by problematic rules and regulations and finally these issues cause organizations to be unable to do their social responsibility. It is expected that there is a relationship between organizational structure and environmental responsibility of managers. Data analysis confirmed it. It was also observed that increase in organizational structure (from mechanical to organic) increases environmental responsibility of managers. It can be argued that in mechanical structures, goals diverted from their main way due to problematic regulations that themselves are a tool for reaching goals but they changed into goal so the organization cannot adapt with the environment. Due to responsibility for predetermined goals, organizations try to realize goals more and more. This effort causes management to ignore its environment and restrain its duty inside the organization and protect organizational interests regardless of society. On the other hand, it prefers organizational interests to social interests. It apparently seems that managers promoted their organizations by this method and take step to improve them but it is not true and in a society where greed, egocentric, exploitation for getting more financial profit and promoting personal position and place have destroyed its elements, it is impossible to have a dynamic and fresh organization. The assumption that there is a relationship between organizational structure and consideration of cultural values was confirmed by obtained evidences. It was also observed that distribution of cultural values in organizational managers who works in very mechanical, organic environments or both of them is the same. It can be said that all managers in the studied society (regardless of structures' kind) insisted averagely on consideration of cultural values. It can be argued that values express basic beliefs in addition to our vigorous faith and religion. They are stable and do not simply undergo changes and they are considered by managers in the society. Although the kind of structure may create obstacles while considering values, totally it cannot cause lack of consideration of values specially in mechanical structures because organizations lose from lack of consideration of cultural values so managers try to consider cultural values by different methods because they know that lack of paying attention to values damages their organizational popularity and fame and the organization will lose its customers, shareholders and even employers. Lack of consideration of cultural values such as disclosing crime, promising, punishment of offenders makes the organization repugnant to view of the society.

Recommendations

Regarding research results, it is recommended that

- 1- The kind of organizational structure from mechanical to organic one and redesign of structures should be reviewed by organizations
- 2- Training periods should be held to explain social responsibility, disadvantages of mechanical structures (traditional) and training redesign of structures to managers with emphasis on organic features
- 3- Regarding importance and clarity of social responsibility, this parameter should be measured in different dimensions.

4- It is suggested that other obstacles in the way of social responsibility of managers should be studied and some suggestions are made for solving them.

5- It is suggested that the research results are given to managers of institutions and offices in order to increase knowledge and encourage next cooperation.

6- It is suggested that similar researches are done in other provinces and obtained results are compared with results of this study.

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